

TOURISM DYNAMICS: NAVIGATING MODERN TRAVEL ALONG THE ANCIENT ROUTE DELVE INTO CONTEMPORARY TOURISM TRENDS, CHALLENGES, AND OPPORTUNITIES ON THE SILK ROAD, EMPHASIZING SUSTAINABLE AND RESPONSIBLE TRAVEL

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Annotation. The article examines the dynamics of tourism and travel along ancient routes, with special emphasis on the Silk Road. Current trends, challenges and opportunities for sustainable tourism development in this context are discussed. Describes the problem of overcrowding of tourist sites and the need to preserve cultural heritage in tourism development and proposes tourism management strategies, educational programs and support for local communities to achieve more sustainable tourism development.

Key words: tourism, routes, silk road, sustainable development, overload, heritage.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada Ipak yo'liga alohida urg'u berilgan holda qadimiy yo'llar bo'ylab sayyohlik va sayohat dinamikasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Ushbu kontekstda turizmni barqaror rivojlantirishning hozirgi tendentsiyalari, muammolari va imkoniyatlari muhokama qilinadi. Turistik ob'ektlarning haddan tashqari ko'pligi muammosini va turizmni rivojlantirishda madaniy merosni saqlash zarurligini tavsiflaydi va turizmni yanada barqaror rivojlantirishga erishish uchun turizmni boshqarish strategiyalari, ta'lim dasturlari va mahalliy hamjamiyatlarni qo'llab-quvvatlashni taklif qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: туризм, маршруты, шелковый путь, устойчивое развитие, перегрузка, наследие.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается динамика туризма и путешествий по древним маршрутам, с особым акцентом на шелковом пути. Обсуждаются текущие тенденции, проблемы и возможности устойчивого развития туризма в этом контексте. Описывается проблема перегрузки туристических объектов и необходимость сохранения культурного наследия при развитии туризма и предлагаются стратегии управления туристическим потоком, образовательные программы и поддержка местных сообществ для достижения более устойчивого развития туризма.

Ключевые слова: туризм, маршруты, шелковый путь, устойчивое развитие, перегрузка, наследие.

The Silk Road, a historical trade route that spanned thousands of years between East and West, is one of the most significant routes for the exchange of goods, cultural ideas and religious practices. The name "Silk Road" comes from the silk trade, but the route included not only this valuable commodity, but also many others, such as spices, silk fabrics, precious metals, weapons, and even religious and philosophical ideas.

The Great Silk Road has significant potential in the development of tourism and tourism products based on the unique and extremely rich heritage, nature and traditions of dozens of

different peoples and cultures along the eternal route [1]¹. In 138 BC. Chinese diplomat and military commander Zhang Jiang first opened the route from China to the countries of Central Asia. By the second half of the 2nd century BC. Central Asia becomes a region connecting two main parts of trade routes leading to Central Asia: from the West (from the Mediterranean countries) and from the East (from China, the Han Empire). Thus, Central Asia became the main and longest link in connecting trade routes into the first historical transcontinental system of trade routes (caravan roads) leading from China to the countries of the Middle East and Europe [2]².

The Silk Road also played an important role in the spread of religious and philosophical ideas such as Buddhism, Christianity, Islam, Taoism and Confucianism. This exchange of cultural ideas stimulated the development and improvement of technology, arts, sciences and architecture along the entire route. Specific cities and regions along the Silk Road, such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Kashgar, Karwan Sarai, Aleppo, Constantinople, and Venice, played an important role in its functioning as a trade and cultural route. The fabulous mosques and madrassas of Khiva, Bukhara and Samarkand, with their amazing architecture and magnificent tiles, are only a small part of what is related to the Silk Road. Tours to Uzbekistan are interesting primarily because they reveal ancient and modern Uzbek culture to the world. Uzbekistan is one of the most famous countries not only in the region, but also in the whole world in terms of historical heritage. Cultural monuments are significant phenomena of every state. Having visited Uzbekistan, the traveler will touch a piece of the spiritual heritage of the civilization of Central Asia - the monuments of the ancient culture of the historical cities of Uzbekistan. Time has preserved for us the unique world of medieval architecture of sacred Bukhara, crowned with the blue domes of Samarkand and minarets reaching towards the sun of Khiva. Once you see, you will never forget the images of Registan or Shakhi-Zinda in Samarkand, the Samanid mausoleum and the Kalyan minaret in Bukhara, the Pakhlavan Mahmud mausoleum and the Juma mosque in Khiva, and you will become an admirer of these and other masterpieces of historical architecture of Uzbekistan [3]³. In 1993, UNWTO began a project to develop the Silk Road as a tourism concept. In 1994, the Samarkand Declaration was adopted, introducing a special logo for use by all participants. The forums became regular after that. In 2002, the Bukhara Declaration was adopted, stimulating environmental and cultural tourism along the route. In 1997, they published a brochure on the tourism potential of the Silk Road, which was highly appreciated by the project participants.

If we talk about Samarkand, it is one of the oldest cities in Central Asia, and occupies a special place on the Silk Road. The capital of Timur, the great conqueror and ruler of Central Asia in the 14th century, Samarkand was the center of trade, culture and science in the region. The city was famous for its luxurious palaces, mosques and madrassas, which attracted merchants, scientists and artists from all over the world. And one of the most famous architectural monuments of Samarkand is Registan, a square surrounded by beautiful madrassas. This architectural ensemble is an excellent example of medieval urbanism and served as an important center of education and cultural exchange along the Silk Road.

¹ Umaraliev, R. A., & Khetagurova, V. Sh. (2014). Velikij Shjolkovyj put' kak osnova social'no-ekonomicheskoy integracii: sovremennoe videnie [The Great Silk Road as a basis of socio-economic integration: a modern vision]. In coll.: Fundamental'nye i prikladnye issledovaniya: problemy i rezul'taty [Basic and applied research: challenges and results]: Proceedings of the Intern. Scient.-pract. conf. Moscow, 225-229. (In Russ.).

² Гумбольдт А. Центральная Азия (тт. 1-3, 1843, рус. пер., т.1), типо-лит. И.Н. Кушнерева, 1915. С. 616.

³ Khetagurova, V. Sh. (2017). Discovering Central Asia: The prospects for tourism development along the paths of the Great Silk Road. p.7.(In Russ).

As we know, modern tourism is developed in the city of Samarkand, that is, this is a type of tourism along ancient routes, including the Silk Road, which is characterized by high development dynamics and a constant increase in popularity among travelers. Along with this, there is an increase in the number of tourists keen to explore the historical and cultural attractions along the route, as well as to gain unique experiences related to thousands of years of history of trade and the exchange of ideas. An important aspect of modern tourism is the variety of offerings for travelers, including excursions, cultural events, and outdoor activities such as hiking and cycling. This varied approach caters to different interests and preferences of tourists, making the experience of traveling along ancient routes more attractive and accessible. But it is also worth noting that with the development of information technology and the Internet, tourists are becoming more informed and independent in planning their trips to Samarkand and beyond. Online resources such as websites, applications and social networks play an important role in disseminating information about tourist routes, attractions, hotels and restaurants along the Silk Road, which notably promote tourism in the region, but also help to quickly and efficiently assist the tourist. According to experts, the tourism industry is one of the most profitable sectors of the economy of the region in question. This industry covers numerous sectors of the economy and various connections between them [4]⁴.

It should also be noted about sustainable tourism, which plays a key role in preserving the cultural and natural heritage along the Silk Road and ensuring its preservation for future generations. This approach to tourism seeks to meet the needs of today's tourists without compromising the ability of future generations to enjoy the same resources.

The impressive spaces of Central Asia are attracting an increasing number of foreign tourists. Cultural and natural sites previously inaccessible to foreign visitors are included in excursion tours. Basically, the routes cover a variety of cultural and historical monuments along the routes of the Great Silk Road. The popularity of tourist trips along the Silk Road routes is constantly growing. The route is becoming more accessible every year thanks to the development of infrastructure and the region's economy [5]⁵.

The development of the tourism industry in the region opens up new economic opportunities, but at the same time creates some risks. The problem arises of how, on the one hand, to provide local communities with the opportunity to enjoy all the benefits from tourism development, and on the other hand, how to ensure that tourism helps to preserve and contribute to the sustainable development of natural and cultural resources.

In the context of the Silk Road, sustainable tourism includes a range of initiatives and practices aimed at minimizing the negative impacts of tourism on the environment, cultural heritage and social structures of local communities. This may include:

1. Nature and environmental conservation: Strategies to reduce resource consumption, reduce waste and maintain biodiversity in regions visited by tourists.
2. Preservation of cultural heritage: Programs for the protection and restoration of historical and cultural monuments, as well as respect for the cultural traditions and customs of local communities.

⁴ Khetagurova, V. Sh. (2017). Discovering Central Asia: The prospects for tourism development along the paths of the Great Silk Road. p.3.(In Russ).

⁵ Umaraliev, R. A., & Khetagurova, V. Sh., (2012). Provodnik kul'turnyh tradicij [Guide of cultural traditions]. Avtomobil'nye dorogi [Car roads], 5, 153-155. (In Russ.).

3. Supporting local development: Initiatives to support local businesses, develop infrastructure and improve the living standards of local people to reduce dependence on tourism and promote sustainable regional development.

4. Education and Awareness: Programs to educate tourists and local people about the importance of conservation of nature and cultural heritage, as well as responsible tourism practices.

Although tourism along ancient routes, including the Silk Road, represents a unique and attractive experience for travelers, there are a number of issues that must be considered to ensure the sustainability of this type of tourism.

One of the main problems is the overload of tourist sites in cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara and Lianyuan, which can lead to the deterioration of architectural structures and the destruction of historical monuments. This problem requires the development of strategies for managing tourist flows and protecting historical sites. At the same time, the development of tourism can have a negative impact on the preservation of the cultural heritage of the region. The commercialization of cultural places, the distortion of their authenticity and the loss of values are becoming real threats. To effectively preserve cultural heritage, it is necessary to develop an integrated approach, including restricting access to sites, developing educational programs for tourists and financial support for programs for the preservation and restoration of cultural monuments, which was already mentioned above.

To solve the problems, some of the following options have been proposed related to the overload of tourist sites and the preservation of cultural heritage:

1. Developing sustainable tourist routes: Creating alternative routes and attracting tourists to lesser-known but equally significant historical sites can help reduce congestion at popular attractions.

2. Introduction of a pre-registration system: The introduction of a pre-registration system for visiting the most popular tourist sites can help control and distribute tourist flows more evenly.

3. Create educational programs for tourists: Conducting educational programs about cultural heritage and the importance of its conservation can increase tourists' awareness and respect for local traditions and customs.

These proposals can help diversify the approach to solving problems and ensure more sustainable tourism development, taking into account the preservation of cultural heritage.

Overall, tourism along ancient routes, especially the Silk Road, is a unique experience that combines history, culture and adventure. However, to ensure its sustainable development, it is necessary to balance the needs of modern travelers with the preservation of natural and cultural resources for future generations. Integrating sustainable tourism practices and working together with local communities, governments and the tourism industry can help preserve the unique heritage of ancient routes and ensure their accessibility for future generations.

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